

15th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, GHGT-15

15th 18th March 2021 Abu Dhabi, UAE

Innovative synergy CCUS and renewable energy project offshore Baltic using CO₂ emissions from the cement industry

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Abstract

The concept of techno-ecological synergy of CO₂ Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) project with different eco-friendly renewable energy recovery technologies, which support circular economy targets, is presented for the first time. The upgraded concept of the CCUS project includes five innovative elements of techno-ecological synergy: (1) CO₂ Geological Storage, (2) Geothermal energy recovery during CO₂ geological storage, (3) Using CO₂ for Enhanced Oil Recovery, (4) solar energy and (5) wind energy recovery. This concept should maximize efficiency, minimize the carbon footprint of the full-chain CCUS process and demonstrate “win^x” situation (where “x” is a number of additional benefits of the project). In the current study we demonstrated an example of the project supporting a win-win-win-win situation (that is, a win-win scenario with a minimum of four potential outcomes) or win⁴ situation: (1) greenhouse gas emissions (GHGE) reduction, (2) economic profitability, (3) increased CO₂ storage capacity and (4) public acceptance. It is planned to capture, transport and isolate 175.2 Mt CO₂ from the atmosphere produced by Estonian Kunda Nordic Cement plant and Eesti Power Plant, Latvian TEC-2 Power Plant and Lithuanian Akmene Cement plant during 30 years of the project duration. Captured CO₂ will be transported by pipelines and ships. The estimated total transport distance for all emissions from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania together by pipelines and ships is 1143.5 km. We considered drilling six wells: three injection wells, two recovery wells for oil and geothermal energy and one monitoring well. Small wind offshore floating plant will be installed around the rig and solar panels will cover all available free surfaces of the rig. Produced solar, wind and geothermal energy will be added to the project electricity net to cover energy needs of the project, e.g. CO₂ injection, fluids recovery, CO₂ separation and reinjection, and for selling energy outside the project to the electric grid. Our Baltic offshore scenario is ambitious and innovative, considering proposed new technologies, synergy with renewable energy, eco-friendly techno-ecological synergy, large storage capacity and included cluster of emission sources from the cement industry and energy production from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. These all listed facts make this concept unique and pioneer in the region and in the CCUS and GHGE field of study.

Keywords: CO₂ geological storage; CO₂ use; CO₂ transport; greenhouse gas emissions reduction; renewable energy; geothermal energy recovery; enhanced oil recovery; Baltic offshore; cement industry emissions; wind energy; solar energy; techno-ecological synergy

1. Introduction

According to the targets of the Paris Climate Agreement, Estonia is aiming to decrease greenhouse gas emissions (GHGE) in 2050 by nearly 80% compared to 1990. To reach these targets by 2030 about 70% of GHGE and by 2040 about 72% of GHGE should be reduced. GHGE has to be decreased by 2050 the most (67%) in the energy sector and industry. The largest CO₂ emitter in Estonia, the Eesti Power Plant has decreased their emissions already almost by 50% implementing in 2019 a new strategy: to buy energy from the Russian energy sector and to develop the renewable energy sector. This plan is looking very promising but unfortunately has very strong and dangerous gaps due to the lack or absolute absence of risk management and economic modelling. Considering the negligence in making such strategic decisions, we are confident that our scenario will be soon actual again. Otherwise, the presented here idea of techno-ecological synergy (TES) could be implemented in any similar projects around the world, improving it and

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making the project greener and including more win-win factors in terms of economics, public acceptance, environmental protection and GHGE. At the moment of this paper writing, Estonia has already met an economic problem related to this decision: a shortage of the produced energy during unpredictable cold winter 2020–2021, high energy prices in the European net and rising CO₂ price in EU ETS, which is obligatory added to the energy price produced by fossil fuel.

Another regular large emitter of CO₂ in Estonia and other European countries is cement plants. The EU Horizon 2020 project CLEANKER is focused on the pilot installation of Ca-looping capture of CO₂ emissions produced by BUZZI Unicem cement plant in northern Italy. The CLEANKER project also includes techno-economic modelling of CO₂ transport, storage and utilization scenarios, including the Baltic regional scenario for Kunda Nordic Tsement Plant (KNC), the main Estonian cement producer. As an analog of the Northern Lights CCS project in Norway [1], which includes industrial CO₂ captured by Norcem Cement Plant in Brevik and by the waste-to-energy plant in Oslo, transported by two ships to the offshore storage site under the North Sea seabed at the depth of 3 km with an estimated capacity of 100 Mt, we are proposing CO₂ Capture, Utilization and Storage (CCUS) scenario offshore Baltic.

CO₂ geological storage (CGS) as a part of CCUS technology is an efficient tool to mitigate climate change and to continue the use of fossil fuels in the energy sector and industry, as a transition technology to a fully renewable energy future. In synergy with Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) technology in the depleted oil reservoirs, the technology can bring in the financial profit and cover part of the CCUS technology costs (CO₂-EOR). CO₂-EOR increases effectively oil production and ensures the permanent storage of large quantities of CO₂ underground (EOR+). In order to reduce CO₂ emissions in the Earth's atmosphere and achieve a win-win situation, captured CO₂ produced by power plants and industry should be used for EOR [2].

The successful synergy of CO₂-EOR and CO₂ storage has been demonstrated already at many places around the world, e.g. Canada, southeast Saskatchewan (Weyburn-Midale CO₂ Monitoring and Storage Project, EnCana Corp.); Russia, the Marjino Deposit, Samara Region (RITEC company, LUKOIL Group); United States, West Texas and New Mexico (Occidental Petroleum, Amerada Hess, Amoco, ARCO, Shell, and Texaco Chevron, Exxon Mobile Corp.); North Sea (BP, Eni, Equinor (Statoil), National Grid, Shell and Total- Northern Endurance Partnership), Lithuania (Minijos Nafta). During more than 40 years, about 600 Mt of CO₂ has been purchased and used in the southwest U.S. Permian Basin alone. For example, in Lithuania CO₂-EOR experiments demonstrated a significant result of 40% of enhanced oil recovery [3]. This extraordinary experience provides strong evidence of the technical feasibility of CCUS technology to permanent capture, storage and economically viable use of CO₂ [4, 5].

The proposed idea is showing how to plan CCUS projects with maximum efficiency, minimize the carbon footprint of the full-chain process, demonstrating “win^x” situation (where “x” is a number of additional benefits of the project). To enhance more the profit of the project and to support a win-win-win-win situation (that is, a win-win scenario with a minimum of four potential outcomes) or win⁴ situation: (1) GHGE, (2) economic profitability, (3) increased CO₂ storage capacity and (4) adequate public acceptance, we upgraded TES, integrating one of the most competitive symbioses of eco-friendly renewable energy systems according to current life cycle assessment and economic studies [6–10]: geothermal energy recovery during CO₂ geological storage (GCS). This synergy has a potential to extract the geothermal heat and sequester carbon dioxide at the same time [11–13]. To implement this modern synergy idea in the specific offshore storage site E6 with very unique properties was recently presented in [4].

Additional surplus of the GCS technology besides the energy recovery showed by [14]. This modeling study shows that geothermal heat extraction from a geologic CO₂ storage formation using CO₂ can eliminate approximately 10% of the reservoir over-pressurization caused by subsurface fluid storage. This degree of pressure management is helping in particular to decrease the lateral extent of reservoir pressure perturbation.

According to [15–16] it is reasonable to recover geothermal energy in reservoirs with a temperature of 65.8°C minimum.

The last but not the least renewable technologies planned to be implemented in our scenario, to make our idea unique, innovative, eco-friendlier and pioneer in TES, are wind energy turbines and solar energy panels installed nearby and at the rig, respectively. Small wind offshore floating plant is planned as an additional collector of energy that will be used for CO₂ injection. Solar panels will cover all free space of the rig covering the everyday energy needs of the rig. The rest of the recovered energy could be sold, using different scenarios, that will be presented in future publications of the authors. During the last two decades the installed global capacity of offshore wind energy increased from 67 megawatts (MW) in 2000 to almost 20 gigawatts (GW) in 2017 and expected to reach 128 GW by 2030, and

521 GW by 2050. The cost of technology is falling down every year and the price of electricity generated by offshore wind accordingly going down, driven by policies such as auctions [17–18]. As mentioned in [18] the part of renewable energy must rise from around 18% of total final energy consumption (in 2015) to around two-thirds by 2050.

Oil companies have significant experience in managing assets offshore and synergies in terms of planned maintenance, defect detection, and asset repair are very strong. Moreover, oil and gas offshore safety standards and management practices are highly transferrable to offshore wind and the skills required to carry out underwater inspection, maintenance and repair could potentially be transferred after minimal re-training, given a highly-skilled workforce and the existence of a comprehensive training infrastructure. In fact, many oil and gas suppliers have successfully provided maintenance and inspection services (e.g., Briggs Marine, 3Sun, Hughes Sub Surface Engineering, Sea Energy and Sub C) [18].

A variety of floating designs have been developed to overcome the depth constraint and to take full advantage of wind resources while benefitting from the less invasive activity on the seabed during installation. The three main concepts for floating foundations are spar-buoy, semi-submersible and tension leg platform. Multiple turbines also could be mounted onto a single floating foundation [18–20].

When applied to solar energy technologies, the outcome of TES produces both technocentric products as well as support for sustainable flows of ecosystem goods and services (for example, CCS, water-use efficiency and habitat for species) that may mitigate global environmental change. Such hybrid renewable energy systems are particularly attractive if they are located in remote places where grid extension and fuel are costly—improving grid reliability (a technological synergistic outcome) while reducing total life-cycle costs [21–23]. It was found in a total of 16 solar energy TESs (win¹⁶) and 20 techno–ecological synergistic outcomes (win²⁰). The scale of ecological outcomes extends from local to global scales [23].

As our Estonian possible prospective CO₂ storage sites are still waiting for their estimation and confirmation, one of the options to reach the targets of this project is to capture Estonian large industrial CO₂ emissions and to transport them for use and geological storage into neighbouring country with available storage capacity.

Our Baltic offshore scenario is ambitious and innovative, considering proposed new technologies, synergy with renewable energy, TES, large storage capacity and included cluster of emission sources from cement industry and energy production from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. Compared to the proposed earlier Baltic onshore CCUS scenario in the CLEANER project, several barriers could be avoided in this offshore scenario, including public resistance, refusal of landlords to permit CO₂ storage at their land in Latvia and construction of wind farms nearby. As recently proposed, coverage of operational costs of the rig, increased oil production (in contrast with conventional CO₂-EOR), geothermal energy recovery (GCS), using benefits from wind and solar energy recovery and increased CO₂ storage capacity are advantages of this concept.

Nomenclature

BS	Baltic States
BSL	Below Sea Level
CCS	CO ₂ Capture and Storage
CCUS	CO ₂ Capture, Utilization and Storage
CGS	CO ₂ Geological Storage
CO ₂ -EOR	Using CO ₂ for Enhanced Oil Recovery
EOR	Enhanced Oil Recovery
EOR+	CO ₂ -EOR applied in synergy with permanent storage of large quantities of CO ₂ underground
EPP	Estonian Eesti Power Plant
EU ETS	EU Emission Trading System
GCS	Geothermal energy recovery during CO ₂ geological storage or CO ₂ Plume Geothermal
GHGE	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
KNC	Estonian Kunda Nordic Tsement plant owned by HeidelbergCement Group
LACP	Lithuanian Akmene Cement plant
TES	Techno–Ecological Synergy
TEC-2	Latvian Power Plant owned by Latvenergo

2. Geological background

The most prospective structures for CGS in the BS are available in Latvia represented by a number of onshore and offshore anticline structures. Estonia was estimated previously out of limits for CGS according to its shallow sedimentary basin and low salinity of aquifer waters [24]. According to new data, Estonian capacity has to be re-estimated. Anyway, at the moment E6 offshore structure is estimated as the most prospective geological structure in the region [24–26].

The E6 offshore structure (Fig. 1) was found by seismic exploration and explored in 1984 by one well E6-1 (depth 1068 m), located 37 km from the coast of Latvia. The structure coincides with the zone of Liepaja-Saldus uplift and was estimated as prospective for oil in 10.5 m thick oil-bearing reservoir layer of the Saldus Formation in the Upper Ordovician Porkuni Stage. The depth range of the oil reservoir in the well is 702–712.5 m. The rocks have good reservoir properties: the open porosity is 10–24% (average 18%), and gas permeability reaches 39 mD (average 6 mD) in the well E6-1. The owner of the license for oil exploitation in the E6 structure is an oil company, Odin Energi Latvia. Oil reserves of the E6 structure estimated by the license owner are 362 MMBO (million barrels of oil) equivalent at the maximum closure of 585 km². Oil flow was very low during exploration: 2.7m³/day from 700 m deep Saldus reservoir due to low pressure within the reservoir and relatively heavy oil.

Prospective for CGS reservoir of the Cambrian Series 3 Deimena Formation (848–901 m depth at the well E6-1) in the E6 structure was assessed as the largest storage site, among all the studied Baltic structures. Oil shows were also found in these sandstones and in the Devonian rocks of the structure (Fig. 1) [2].

The rocks of the Deimena Formation composed of the dark- and light-grey, fine-grained, loosely and medium-cemented quartz oil-impregnated sandstones. The rocks were deposited in a shallow regressing marine basin subjected to tides and storms and are dominated by quartz sandstones with subordinate claystone layers (mud shelf). The poorly sorted sandstones of various grain size, containing gravel fraction, were deposited at the end of Deimena time. The major Deimena reservoir lies regressively on the Kybartai Formation. The regression was associated with the sandier composition of deposits.

Fig. 1. Locations of Latvian onshore structures and the E7 structure offshore Lithuania (brown) prospective for CGS (CO₂ storage potential exceeding 2 Mt) in the Cambrian aquifer and the studied E6 structure offshore Latvia (yellow), with the location of the well, lithological cross-section and gamma-ray logging data, and the 3D geological model of the top of the Cambrian Deimena Formation of the E6 structure. Large regional structures complicating the Baltic Syncline in the study area are shown on the map. The estimated closing contour of the structure is indicated (black contour is –1350 m BSL). Faults bordering the structure are shown by a red wall. The location of the well is shown by a black circle with the depth of the top of the Deimena Formation (–848m BSL). The location of smaller compartment E6-B is indicated by red transparent colour (modified after [2]).

Numerous faults dissect the Cambrian reservoir body. They form important pathways for fluid migration, while high-amplitude faults provide a blockage for fluid migration in the uplifted structures. The structure is an anticline fold bounded on three sides by faults. The E6 structure consists of two different compartments divided by inner fault [27, 28]. The total area of the structure is 600 km² considering the closing contour of the reservoir top located at a depth of 1350 m below sea level (BSL). The average thickness of the reservoir unit is 53 m [4].

Cambrian Series 3 saline aquifer (depth 700–1700 m) located in the central-western part of the Baltic Basin suits best for the CO₂ storage in the Baltic Region. It is composed of 25–80 m thick Deimena Formation sandstone unconformably covered by up to 46 m thick shales and clayey carbonates of primary cap rocks of the Lower Ordovician Zebre Formation. Shale rocks are dark, thin-layered (0.5–2 mm) and highly fissile. A 0.5 m layer of greenish-grey glauconite-bearing sandy marlstones with minor limestone lenses is observed at the base of the onshore Zebre Formation. The reservoir rocks are also covered by 130–230 m thick Ordovician (146 m thick in the well E6-1) and 100–225 m thick Silurian (122 m thick in the well E6-1) impermeable clayey carbonate secondary cap rocks, consisting mainly of shales, marlstones and clayey limestones (Fig. 1) [2, 4].

The porosity of the Cambrian Series 3 Deimena Formation reservoir sandstones is in the range of 14–33% (21% mean) and permeability is in the range of 10–440 mD (170 mD mean). The average porosity and permeability of the Ordovician cap rock are 3% and <0.01mD, respectively. The Cambrian aquifer includes potable water in the northern shallow part of the Baltic Basin, mineral water (salinity 10 g/l) in southern Estonia and saline water in the Deimena Formation at more than 800 m depths, with salinity up to 120 g/l in the central and 150–180 g/l in the southern and western parts of the basin, where the fluid temperature reaches 88°C [29]. The last-mentioned geochemical and pressure-temperature conditions of formation fluids allow the use of the Deimena Formation reservoir for CGS at depths of 800–2500 m, where CO₂ can be stored in a supercritical state (pressure >73 atm and temperature >31°C) [4].

Conservative and optimistic CO₂ storage capacity of the structure was estimated in the range of 160–400 Mt, respectively. The theoretical storage capacity of the Saldus Formation at the end of the CO₂-EOR cycle was estimated as 65–144 Mt with an average 110 Mt. Total capacity of the E6 structure in the Deimena and Saldus formations at the end of CO₂-EOR cycle by optimistic (320–745 Mt, average 490 Mt) and conservative approaches (170–385 Mt, average 265 Mt) were evaluated [30].

We considered CGS and GCS in the Cambrian Deimena Formation with a depth range of 848–901m BSL and temperature in the aquifer 36°C, and CO₂-EOR/EOR+ in the Upper Ordovician Saldus Formation. Including GCS in the concept makes it very attractive due to self-energy support.

3. Data and methods

CO₂ emissions produced in 2019 and reported in EU ETS were used for the CCUS scenario [31]. The methodology developed by CLEANKER project for techno-economic modelling of CCUS scenarios was applied [32]. All geological and technical data needed for scenario modelling were collected into ArcGIS based system created for the CLEANKER project.

For the definition of technical parameters (pipelines diameter and others), we have used the Australian Power Generation Technology Report [33], where the University of Sydney estimated CO₂ transport and storage parameters using information collected from Australian stakeholders. This report provides building block datasets in the form of figures, tables and equations to enable users to estimate costs and performance for the pipeline transportation and CGS. The pipeline diameter was determined depending on the distance and flow-rate of CO₂ calculated for the specific scenario according to Fig. 102 in [33]. Spatial data were collected and the map was constructed using the ArcGIS platform, version 10.6. MS Excel datasheets were designed for data collection and easy use by the CLEANKER project partners.

The storage capacity of the Deimena Formation in the E6 was estimated with different levels of reliability, using Bachu et al. method [30, 34]. Theoretical storage potential of oil-bearing Saldus Formation at the end of CO₂-EOR cycle implementing conservative and optimistic approaches evaluated using equation presented in Bachu [30, 35].

4. Scenario

It is proposed to capture CO₂ from the Kunda Nordic Tsement (KNC), producing about 547 000 t CO₂ per year and from the Eesti Power Plant (EPP) in Estonia, produced about 3.43 Mt CO₂ in 2019 (Table 1). Both plants are located close to the Baltic Sea shore (Fig. 2). Additionally, the Lithuanian Akmeine Cement plant (LACP) produced in 2019 more than 965,272 t CO₂ and Latvian Power plant Latvenergo (TEC-2) producing 898,000 t CO₂ per year, will be included. In total, about 5.5 Mt CO₂ per year could be captured, compressed, transported and used for CO₂-EOR, GCS and, consequently, for CGS (Table 1). During 30 years it is planned to capture, transport and use 166.4 Mt CO₂ and to avoid from the atmosphere 157.7 Mt CO₂, considering the production of CO₂ by participating plants at the level of 2019.

The distance from the TEC-2, located in Salaspils city, close to Riga, to the port of Liepaja to transport captured CO₂ will be covered by pipelines (230 km). LACP located in Lithuania 145 km from the port of Liepaja and planned to be covered by pipelines as well. Latvian and Lithuanian CO₂ emissions will be combined in the port of Liepaja and send by ships to the E6 structure (45 km). We included the KNC- and the EPP-E6 transport distance by pipelines to port and from port to the E6 structure by ships. The distance from the KNC to the Port of Kunda by pipelines is 4.5 km and from the EPP to the port of Sillamäe by pipelines is about 30 km. From the Port of Sillamae, the EPP's emissions will be transported by ship to the Port of Kunda is 74 km. In the Port of Kunda CO₂ emission from the KNC and EPP will be combined and sent to the E6 structure by ship – 615 km (Fig. 2, Table 2).

The total distance planned to be covered by pipelines in Estonia is 34.5 km and in Latvia and Lithuania 375 km. All together 409.5 km. The total distance planned to be covered by pipelines and ships for all planned Estonian CO₂ emissions is 723.5 km and for Latvian and Lithuanian emissions together is 420 km. All together the distance to transport by pipelines and ships emissions from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania is 1099.5 km (Table 2).

Table 1. Technical parameters of the Baltic offshore scenario for 2019.

Country	Estonia		Total Estonian share	Latvia	Lithuania	Total Baltic CCUS
	KNC	Eesti PP (EPP)	2 plants	Latvenergo (TEC-2)	Akmeine Cement plant (LACP)	4 plants
Emissions sources	KNC	Eesti PP (EPP)	2 plants	Latvenergo (TEC-2)	Akmeine Cement plant (LACP)	4 plants
CO ₂ emissions produced per year, Mt	0.55	3.43	3.98	0.90	0.97	5.84
CO ₂ emissions captured (95%), Mt	0.52	3.26	3.78	0.85	0.92	5.55
CO ₂ emissions avoided per year, Mt	0.49	3.09	3.58	0.81	0.87	5.26
Total CO ₂ emissions captured during 30 years, Mt	15.59	97.76	113.34	25.59	27.50	166.44
Total CO ₂ emissions captured during 30 years, %	9.37	58.73	68.10	15.38	16.52	100.00
Total CO ₂ emissions avoided during 30 years, Mt	14.77	92.61	107.38	24.25	26.06	157.68

Table 2. CO₂ pipelines distance and diameter of the Baltic offshore scenario.

Country	Estonia		Total Estonian share	Latvia	Lithuania	Total Baltic CCUS
	KNC	Eesti PP (EPP)	2 plants	Latvenergo (TEC-2)	Akmeine Cement plant (LACP)	4 plants
Emissions sources	KNC	Eesti PP (EPP)	2 plants	Latvenergo (TEC-2)	Akmeine Cement plant (LACP)	4 plants
Pipeline distance to the ports, km/diameter in mm	4.5/100	30/300	34.5	230/250	145/220	409.5
CO ₂ transport by ship, km	615	30+615	645	45	45	690

Fig. 2. Transport model of the proposed innovative synergy CCUS and renewable energy project offshore Baltic using CO₂ emissions from the cement industry and energy production from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. Red line is showing the transport model. Captured CO₂ from Eesti Power Plant (EPP) will be transported to the Port of Sillamäe by pipelines and to the Port of Kunda by ship (all locations in Estonia). CO₂ emissions captured at Kunda Nordic Tsement (KNC) will be transported by pipelines to the Port of Kunda and together with emissions arrived from EPP will be transported by ship to the Latvian offshore structure E6. CO₂ captured at Latvian Power plant Latvenego (TEC-2) and Lithuanian Akme Cement plant (LACP) will be transported by pipelines to the Port of Liepaja (Latvia). Later, combined emissions from TEC-2 and LACP will be transported by ship to the E6.

After CO₂ will arrive at the offshore platform or drilling rig of the E6 storage site, it will be injected into the CO₂ storage reservoir for CGS and GCS and to the oil-bearing reservoir to enhance oil recovery (Fig. 3). We are planning to drill six wells: three wells for injection (one for CO₂-EOR in the Saldus oil reservoir, two for GCS and CGS in the Deimena Formation), two for liquids recovery (one for oil recovery from the Saldus Formation and one for warm water recovery from the Deimena Formation) and one for monitoring. The number of injection wells estimated using average injection capacity for one well is 1.5–1.7 Mt CO₂ per year (depends on properties of rocks in injection formation).

Small wind offshore floating plant is planned to be installed around the rig (Fig. 3). The number of wind generators will be depended on the budget of the project and technical capacity. More generators - more clean energy will be recovered and used for covering energy needs of the rig including CO₂ injection, oil and energy recovery, CO₂ separation and reinjection.

Solar panels will be installed at all available free surfaces of the rig and gained solar energy will be added to the project electricity net for covering energy needs of the project or for selling energy (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Conceptual techno-ecological schematic model of CCUS project with different green renewable energy recovery technologies in the structure E6 including synergy of (1) CGS, (2) GCS, (3) CO₂-EOR/EOR+ in different geological formations in the same storage site and (4) solar energy and (5) wind energy recovery.

5. Discussion

For the first time, in this paper we presented the upgraded concept of the CCUS project which includes five innovative elements of TES: (1) CGS, (2) GCS, (3) CO₂-EOR/EOR+, (4) solar energy and (5) wind energy recovery. The main CCUS concepts CGS, GCS, CO₂-EOR/EOR+ are planned in different geological formations in the same storage site for the specific case of the E6 geological structure offshore Latvia. Profits of the TES and possible risks were analysed. Our sustainable recovery and use of renewable energy concept is demonstrating the idea of how to upgrade CCS/CCUS projects with multiple win-win situation support or win^x (where x is the number of additional benefits or potential outcomes of the project). The idea aims to maximize the efficiency, have a positive impact on public and Green NGO's acceptance of this technology in the region, avoid conflicts during underground use and minimize the carbon footprint of the full-chain CCUS process.

We considered CO₂-EOR/EOR+ in the Upper Ordovician Saldus Formation (702–712.5 m). The CO₂-EOR method has been already tested for the Cambrian Deimena Formation ROZ (residual oil zone) in the Baltic Sea Region by the Lithuanian oil company Minijos Nafta. Two pilot injections have been made into Lithuanian onshore oil fields (about 2 km depth) for EOR+ in 2013, investigating the potential of CO₂ to be used for EOR. The results showed that one tonne of injected CO₂ could produce one tonne of oil from the Cambrian reservoir or 40% of enhanced oil recovery [3]. There are no tests of CO₂-EOR in the Ordovician reservoir and this project will be a pioneer in the region.

We expect good oil recovery with CO₂ and effective hypothetical CO₂ storage capacity in the future depleted oil field due to the large area of the oil-bearing structure. In a contrast with conventional CO₂-EOR, in the proposed scenarios we planned CO₂-EOR at the beginning of oil production. As a result, more oil will be produced than in conventional CO₂-EOR.

CGS and CPG in E6 structure are planned in the Cambrian Deimena Formation with a depth range of 848–901 m BSL and temperature in the aquifer 36°C. Including CPG into the concept makes it very attractive due to self-energy support. But for effective CPG it is estimated recovery reservoir temperature of 65.8°C minimum [15, 16]. The efficiency of this case study will be estimated during further economic modelling, but the concept as it is having importance in terms of sustainable use of underground resources.

The technical profit of GCS is a pressure equilibration in the CO₂ storage/geothermal energy system. During GCS approximately 10% of the reservoir over-pressurization caused by underground CO₂ storage could be eliminated. While relatively small, this degree of pressure management is not inconsequential, helping in particular to decrease the lateral extent of reservoir pressure perturbation [14].

Fault system within the structure which possibly led to the migration of hydrocarbons from the Cambrian reservoir to the upper Ordovician reservoir can represent possible leakage pass way during CO₂ storage. The risk of CO₂ leakage from the Deimena Formation due to uncertainties of the fault system was considered as a profit for CO₂-EOR/EOR+ in the Upper Ordovician Formation. No transmissivity values are available for the faults in the area. Nevertheless, the presence of live-oil in the Saldus Formation gives us the opportunity to assume the integrity of the oil reservoir and the impermeability of the Silurian cap rock. Thereby, CO₂ will stay in the Upper Ordovician with a link to the Cambrian Formation via faults. Furthermore, the largest onshore Inčukalns structure, with a structural setting comparable to E6, has been successfully used for underground gas storage for many years, serving for gas supply to Latvia, Estonia and Lithuania. This fact indicates that faults in the region may have enclosed, impermeable structure and as suggested in [26], faults in the E6 structure can act as sealing surfaces [4].

Floating wind energy turbines installed nearby the rig and solar energy panels will cover all free space of the rig. Wind park and the solar station will cover everyday energy needs of the rig, especially, for CO₂ injection and CO₂ separation from recovered oil. The rest of the recovered energy could be sold, using different scenarios, that will be presented in future publications of authors. These two technologies must be an integral part of any techno-ecological project of our days.

Additional advantages of using E6 structure offshore Latvia are:

- Large storage capacity, provided by CO₂ storage in two reservoirs (Cambrian Deimena Formation and oil-bearing Upper Ordovician Saldus Formation). It was recently evaluated 265–490 Mt of CO₂ storage capacity on average in both formations at the end of the CO₂-EOR cycle by conservative and optimistic approach, respectively.
- Agreement of the oil company Odin Energi Latvia, owner of the oil license of the E6 structure, to cooperate in the CO₂ use and storage project.

- Techno–ecological synergy of CGS, GCS, CO₂-EOR/EOR+, solar energy and (5) offshore wind energy recovery.

The planned project duration is 30 years. In total six wells are planned, including three injection, two oil and geothermal energy recovery and one monitoring. The number of injection wells estimated using the average injection capacity for one well is 1.5–1.7 Mt of CO₂ per year (for the storage formation with good injection properties). To estimate the cost of the project additional economic modeling must be provided according to data presented in this paper.

6. Conclusions

We proposed for the first time the concept of techno–ecological synergy of the CCUS project with different green renewable energy recovery technologies, which support circular economy targets. The upgraded concept of the CCUS project which includes five innovative elements of techno–ecological synergy was presented: (1) CGS, (2) GCS, (3) CO₂-EOR/EOR+, (4) solar energy and (5) wind energy recovery. This concept should maximize efficiency, minimize the carbon footprint of the full-chain process and demonstrate win^x situation (where x is a number of additional benefits of the project).

In this study, we planned to capture, transport and isolate 175.2 Mt CO₂ from the atmosphere produced by Estonian KNC and EPP, Latvian TEC-2 and Lithuanian LACP during 30 years of the project duration. Captured CO₂ is planned to transport by pipelines and ships. The total distance planned to be covered by pipelines in Estonia is 34.5 km and in Latvia and Lithuania 375 km. All together 409.5 km. The total distance planned to be covered by pipelines and ships for all planned Estonian CO₂ emissions is 723.5 km and for Latvian and Lithuanian emissions together is 420 km. The total distance for all emissions from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania together planned to be transported by pipelines and ships is 1143.5 km.

We considered drilling in total six wells: three injection wells, two liquids recovery wells and one monitoring well. Two wells were planned for CO₂ injection for CGS and GCS in the Cambrian Deimena Formation with a depth range of 848–901 m BSL and one for warm water recovery from the Formation. Another CO₂ injection well was planned for CO₂-EOR/EOR+ in the Upper Ordovician Saldus Formation (702–712.5 m) and one well for oil recovery. The last well was planned for CO₂ storage monitoring.

Small wind offshore floating plant is planned to be installed around the rig and solar panels will cover all available free surfaces of the rig. Produced solar, wind and geothermal energy will be added to the project electricity net to cover energy needs of the project, e.g. CO₂ injection, fluids recovery, separation and CO₂ reinjection, and/or for selling energy outside the project to the electric grid.

Our Baltic offshore scenario is ambitious and innovative, considering proposed new technologies, synergy with renewable energy, techno–ecological synergy, large storage capacity and included cluster of emission sources from cement industry and energy production from Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. These all listed facts make this concept unique and pioneer in the region and in the CCUS and GHGE field of study.

The current concept study is planned to be updated in a further publication with new amazing futuristic performance ideas and economic estimations and will make our concept more beneficial and productive for society, greener, and environmentally friendly.

Acknowledgments

This study is supported by CLEANER project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement n. 764816. This work is supported by the China Government (National Natural Science Foundation of China) under contract No.91434124 and No.51376105.

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